
THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN AND THE ROLE OF TRANSPORT SERVICES IN IT

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8232051>

Nuriddinova Durдона is the daughter of Shukhrat

Asian International University.

MM-5 group students Iqt 22.

Abstract

In this article, tourist services, their structure, the organization of transport services in the field of tourism, the development of tourism services in Uzbekistan, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" for 2022-2026 Analytical information such as the goals of tourism development, the importance of researching the transport infrastructure in tourism, the change of the role of transport in tourism, and the factors of the tourist attraction of the Republic of Uzbekistan are highlighted.

Keywords

Transport, "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan", transport infrastructure, tourism, tourist services, tourist resources, tourist attraction, domestic and foreign tourism.

Transport is one of the most important components of the material base of the economy of any country. Since ancient times, transport has been the engine of progress. Man used any means at hand to transport people and goods. With the invention of the wheel, and a little later, various types of engines, a person began to develop vehicles, respectively: wagons, carriages, steamboats, steam locomotives, airplanes, etc. This made it possible to travel long distances and for various purposes

Currently, transport is one of the most important components of the economy of the state, both developing and with a highly developed economic and social base. Transport ensures the normal functioning of the economy, increases the efficiency of social production, creates conditions for the rational distribution of production forces throughout the country, taking into account the most appropriate approximation of enterprises in various sectors of the economy to sources of raw materials and areas of consumption of products, specialization and cooperation of production, allows the development of industries such as trade, agriculture and others. Transport is a leading factor in the development of tourism

The role of transport is great in solving social problems, ensuring business, cultural and tourist trips of the population, developing cultural exchange within the country and abroad.¹

Today, the tourism industry is one of the fastest growing sectors of the world economy. Like other sectors of the economy, this sector also plays an important role in the development of the country. Because through the development of tourism, additional jobs are created, employment of the population is ensured, and the well-being of the nation increases. In short, the infrastructure will improve.

According to data, more than 1 billion people travel to different countries every year. 10% of the world's gross domestic product, 7% of the world's exports, and about 8% of the working population belong to the tourism sector. The tourism potential of our country is high, but it is time to do a lot of work in this area. Reforms for the development of the industry are gaining momentum.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" for 2022-2026, the goals of tourism development include:²

1. To increase the number of domestic tourists from 12 million and increase the number of foreign tourists visiting the republic to 9 million within the framework of the "Travel around Uzbekistan" program.

2. Broad introduction of barrier-free tourism infrastructure in the main tourism cities of the country. By 2026, the number of people employed in tourism should be doubled to 520,000.

3. Adoption of the state program on the development of the infrastructure of tourism and cultural heritage objects and the effective use of more than 8 thousand cultural heritage objects.

4. Construction of additional tourist zones and recreation centers in Zomin, Forish, Bakhmal districts and "Aydar-Arnasoy" lake system, implementation of projects worth 300 million US dollars, creation of 25,000 jobs.

5. To increase the volume of tourism services by at least 10 times in the next five years by turning Samarkand into a "Tourism Gate". Ensuring employment of 40,000 people in the field of tourism. In 2022, the establishment of the Samarkand tourism center, including the historical complex "Eternal City", and the necessary infrastructure.

¹ https://tourlib.net/books_tourism/zorin11.htm

² <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-5841063>

6. Implementation of a special program for the development of ecotourism in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the island coast. In this case, wide use of the possibilities of the new airport of Moynak.

7. To adopt a special program for tourism to be the main driving force in the creation of new jobs in Khorezm region.

8. Implementation of a special program for rapid development of tourism in Bukhara region.

9. Effective use of pilgrimage and ecotourism potential in Navoi region.

10. Further improvement of tourism infrastructure in Tashkent city.

11. Development of a separate program for bringing the tourism potential to a new level in the Tashkent region.

12. Development of a single transport system that integrates all types of transport, creating an opportunity to reach and return to the destination on the basis of daily transport between large cities.

13. Improvement of public transport system and development of its infrastructure in Tashkent city and regions.

14. Increasing the attractiveness of intercity and suburban railway services.

15. Development of the market and infrastructure of transport and logistics services, raising the level of electrification of the railway infrastructure to 60% and rapid development of the highway network.

16. Expansion of "green corridors" and transit opportunities for foreign trade in the field of transport and increase of the volume of transit cargo to 15 million tons.

The importance of researching tourism transport infrastructure is determined by the changing role of transport in tourism. Transport becomes not only a means of transport that ensures the availability of tourism resources and is an indicator of the level of development of the network, but also has the characteristics of a tourism resource.

Tourism is a social, cultural and economic phenomenon associated with the movement of people to places outside their permanent place of residence, and the motive is usually entertainment and recreation. Uzbekistan attracts the attention of the whole world with its numerous ancient historical and architectural monuments, rich nature and rapid modern progress. The IchanKala complex in Khiva, the historical centers of Bukhara, Shakhrisabz and Samarkand are included in a special UNESCO list - "World Heritage". Unique monuments and architectural structures

in these cities are a reflection of an era that played a significant role in the history of the country.³

Table 1

A set of factors of tourist attraction of the Republic of Uzbekistan ⁴

Factors of tourist attractiveness of the Republic of Uzbekistan	Factors of attracting tourists in the Republic of Uzbekistan
Natural recreation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - favorable environmental conditions; - presence of interesting natural objects and monuments; - video-ecological characteristics of landscapes; - availability of balneological resorts and sanatoriums; - natural state of natural landscapes; - features of the geological and geomorphological structure of the area;
Cultural and historical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - presence of architectural and archaeological monuments; - conducting music and folklore festivals; - organization and holding of fairs, exhibitions; - activities of museums, museum complexes; - existence and preservation of traditional people - existence of folklore monuments and holding traditional and religious holidays; - availability of religious and religious pilgrimage sites;
Organizational, economic and production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - state protectionism of tourism development; - formation of modern tourist infrastructure; - availability of organizational

³ file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/18.Tourist%20flows.pdf

⁴ https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/226290314.pdf

	<p>opportunities for the development of various types of tourism in the republic;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the existence of organizational and economic possibilities of directing social production to provide services to tourists; - possibilities to accommodate a large number of tourists;
Socio-psychological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - availability of sufficient amount of tourist products; - existence of specific national-cultural foundations and goodwill of the local population; - availability of guarantees for the safety and comfort of tourists.

Tourists who arrived in the first quarter of 2023 by air amounted to 198.3 thousand people (13.3%), by rail – 21.8 thousand people (1.5%), by road – 6.5 thousand people (0.4%). The largest number were backpackers – 1 261.1 thousand people (84.8%).

According to the data of the State Statistics Committee, in July 2023, the prices of tourist travel services increased by 6.6% on average compared to June. Since the beginning of the year, the prices of tourist travel services have increased by an average of 7.8% and compared to the same month of the previous year, that is, they have increased by an average of 10.1% on an annual basis. At the moment, there are positive trends in the rapid recovery of tourism in Uzbekistan, and up to 4.5 million foreign tourists are expected to come to our country by the end of 2023.

Only in July 2023, 540,700 foreign citizens came to Uzbekistan for tourist purposes. According to the information of the State Statistics Committee, this indicator has increased by 3 times compared to the same period last year.

Domestic tourism is also rapidly developing in our country. In particular, as a result of the implementation of the "Travel Uzbekistan" program, the number of domestic tourists is increasing every year. The development of domestic and foreign tourism is also caused by the improvement of tourism infrastructure.⁵

Despite the above positive changes, a number of problems are evident in the process of using transport services in the tourism sector of our country. In order to prevent these problems, we would like to give a number of suggestions and recommendations:

First of all, the absence of a single logistics center and its inter-country departments among the Central Asian countries has a negative impact on the socio-economic relations between the countries, especially the visa-free movement of tourists between the countries. If the countries of Central Asia try to maintain their place in the world community, which is developing at a fast pace, they should create a space without internal borders, similar to the countries of the European Union, to long-term economic development coordinated by strengthening economic and social interaction. help, organize an economic and monetary union and create a single currency, conduct a joint foreign policy and security policy, and in the future conduct a joint defense policy, establish a unique uniformity in the international sphere, cooperate in the field of justice and internal affairs it would be appropriate to develop, preserve and increase the common wealth. In this process, the use of a single logistics center would help the countries to increase the tourist flow.

Secondly, the tourism strategy of the Central Asian regional economic cooperation until 2030 was drawn up, and this strategy provides a general strategic and coherent framework for the direction of tourism activities in the Central Asian region until 2030. It defines the long-term perspective, guiding principles, strategic framework and goals for sustainable development in the region, development of safe and inclusive tourism, and increasing its attractiveness as a world-class competitive tourism destination. It is based on the results and recommendations of the study on the development of regional tourism cooperation in 2018 within the framework of CAREC 2030. The tourism development strategy is aligned with the general direction of the CAREC 2030 Strategy, as well as with the priorities and plans of countries in the field of tourism, and aims to ensure close coordination of

⁵ <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/turistik-sayohat-xizmatlari-narxlari-bir-oyda-ortacha-66--ga-oshgan>

tourism initiatives implemented by development partners in the region. It would be appropriate if our country took an active part in these directions and implemented the main goals of the strategy in various aspects of the economy.⁶

REFERENCES:

1. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/226290314.pdf>
2. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yevropa_Ittifoqi
3. file:///F:/Users/user/Desktop/Jo'rayevaZ.T.%20maqola/CAREC-Tourism-Strategy_Final-Draft-ru.pdf
4. Rajabova M. Creation of free economic zones in Bukhara: problems and solutions //Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 7. – №. 7.
5. Djabbarov I. Problems of Organization of Tourist Zones in Free Economic Zones of Bukhara //Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 5. – №. 5.
6. Yavmutov D. S. Opportunities for the development of non-traditional tourism in Bukhara //International scientific review of the problems of economics, finance and management. – 2020. – С. 15-21.
7. Rajabova M. FEATURES OF THE PRODUCTION OF TOURIST ROUTES //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 7. – №. 7.
8. Dustova A. Stimulating The Economic Growth Of Territories Through The Development Of Regional Tourism //Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz). – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 12.
9. Бобоев А. Ч., Базарова М. С. ХОРИЖИЙ ИНВЕСТИЦИЯЛАРНИНГ ЖОЗИБАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ //Интернаука. – 2019. – №. 22-3. – С. 88-90.
10. Bazarova M. S. FACTORS THAT ENSURE THE SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION OF A SYSTEM OF KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS IN THE FIELD OF HIGHER EDUCATION //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 11. – С. 582-586.
11. Базарова М. С., Шарипова М., Нуруллоев О. “РАҚАМЛИ ИҚТИСОДИЁТ” ДА АҲОЛИНИНГ ИШ БИЛАН БАНДЛИГИ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //САМАРҚАНД ДАВЛАТ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ. – 2021. – С. 482.

⁶ file:///F:/Users/user/Desktop/Jo'rayevaZ.T.%20maqola/CAREC-Tourism-Strategy_Final-Draft-ru.pdf

12. Алимova Ш. А., Ниёзова И. Н. Бизнес-коммуникации в системе управления промышленных структур // Academy, (1 (64)). – 2021. – С. 55-57.
13. Alimova S. A., Nutfullaevna K. M. STATE MANAGEMENT OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC ACTIVITY OF ENTERPRISES // Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 10. – С. 75-80.
14. Алимova Ш. А., Халимова Д. Р. СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ СУЩНОСТЬ СТРАТЕГИЙ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН // Современные проблемы социально-экономических систем в условиях глобализации. – 2021. – С. 340-344.
15. Базарова М. С., Ходжиева Ш. С. ЦЕЛИ И ЗАДАЧИ СТРАТЕГИИ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН // Современные проблемы социально-экономических систем в условиях глобализации. – 2020. – С. 170-173.